

COVID-19 ON CRICKET ECONOMY

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Abstract:

Cricket game is like a religion in India which has a huge fan following. According to the market research conducted by the International Cricket Council (ICC), cricket has over a billion fans across the world with the Indian alone constituting around 90 percent of them. Therefore, cricket is big religion in India. Cricket is playing in every nook and corner of India. The commencement of the IPL brought in huge revenue for the BCCI and for the Indian economy. According to a study of revealed that in 2015, the revenue of the IPL was Rs.2605 crores and it has contributed to India's Gross Domestic Product was Rs.1150 crores. So, the IPL has increased the BCCI revenues, it also resulted in greater tax contributions, which means higher government revenues. BCCI has paid around Rs 3,500 crore as tax since the financial year 2007 – 2008. So, cricket is not playing anywhere in the world. Because of the cancellation of the IPL due to covid-19 the BCCI is losing around Rs 3,000 crores.

Key Words: Covid -19, Cricket & Economy

Introduction:

Cricket game is like a religion in India which has a huge fan following. According to the market research conducted by the International Cricket Council (ICC), cricket has over a billion fans across the world with the Indian alone constituting around 90 percent of them. Therefore, cricket is big religion in India. Cricket is playing in every nook and corner of India. From cities to remote villages children are playing cricket, while the elders watch or listen to cricket matches. To capitalize on the situation the BCCI has introduced the IPL in year 2008. By introducing a domestic cricket league within few years after its inception, it became the most profit making annual sporting event of BCCI.

Objectives of the Study:

- To study corona-19 impact all over the world.
- To study corona-19 effect on sports and games.
- To study the pandemic outcome on cricket.
- To identify the factors which caused huge loss of revenue to the global cricket.

Methodology:

The article is widely bank upon secondary sources. The data and information related to the cricket economy have been collected from various articles which were published in various daily news papers and from internet also. Further, all the collected information is presented in such way, so that meaningful inferences would be drawn.

Literature Review:

- Vaishnavi Kanukurti attempts on "The Economics of the Indian Premier League" describes cricket more than a game is like a religion in India which has huge fan following. Further, says cricket has over a billion fans globally with the Indian sub-continent alone constituting more than 90 percent of them.
- B. G. Clarkson, A. Culvin, S. Pope in their study on "Covid-19, Reflection on threat and uncertainty for the future of elite Women's football in England", speaks covid-19 is likely to impact the livelihoods of professional footballers, particularly women who operate have also risen amid concerns about the longevity and implications of Covid-19. So, it will affect the mental health issues of the sports persons.
- R. Schinke, A. Papaioannou, K. Hansiksen, G. Sil, L. Zhang efforts on "Sports psychology services to high Performance athletes during Covid-19" explains these are trying times for us all, Covid-19 has altered our lives as Citizens. The changes associated with the current pandemic have presented sports and exercise psychologists with many challenges and opportunities related to sport performance.
- S. Feng, C. Shen, N. Xia, W. Song, M. Fan works on "Rational use of face masks in the Covid-19 pandemic" says, since the outbreak of severe acute respiratory syndrome Corona- 19 2(SARS-cov-2) the virus that caused Corona-19 (Corona-19), the use of face masks has become ubiquitous in China and other Asian countries.
- W. J. Mckibbin, R. Fernando throws light on "The Global Macra Economic impact of Covid-19" Severe, Scenarios make clear that the outbreak of corona-19 has disrupted the Chinese economy and is spreading globally. The evolution of the disease and its economic impact is highly uncertain which makes it difficult for policy makers to formulate an appropriate macroeconomic policy.

Revenue from Cricket Economy:

The commencement of the IPL brought in huge revenue for the BCCI and for the Indian economy. According to a study of revealed that in 2015, the revenue of the IPL was Rs.2605 crores and it has contributed to India's Gross Domestic Product was Rs.1150 crores. Therefore, an analysis of the economics of the IPL with respect to its macro-level contributions to the Indian economy and micro-level contributions to the teams and the players makes good sense at this juncture.

So, the IPL has increased the BCCI revenues, it also resulted in greater tax contributions, which means higher government revenues. BCCI has paid around Rs 3,500 crore as tax since the financial year 2007 – 2008. Till then the BCCI did not pay taxes as it was considered a charitable organization. However, after the commencement of the IPL, the Income Tax department declared that IPL has an economic and commercial activity. Thereafter, the BCCI has been paying tax amount to Rs 350 crore a year.

Now, the IPL has become one of the BCCI's most successful ventures which accounts for nearly 95 percent of the board surplus as compared to the rest of the board operations. This obviously speaks that the BCCI is making its most profit during the IPL than the rest of the year. Since international players also earn a fair amount during the IPL, over the years there have been little to no international cricket tournaments taking place during IPL season so that all players are available. Therefore, the bargaining strength and influence of the BCCI has increased in tandem with other cricket boards among the cricketing world.

With the surplus money from the IPL, the BCCI has been able to increase cricket activities regularly at the National Cricket Academy (NCA) by allocating Rs.50 crores in 2018 as compared to the Rs. 26 crores it allocated in 2017. There has also been an increase in domestic cricket matches along with a strengthening in women and junior cricket, it is all happening due to the success of the IPL. Thus, the IPL has allowed for greater cricket development which can result in better cricket players and even improve India's performance in cricket at the international level. Our Indian team is one of the best teams in all forms of Cricket. Whether it is one day, T20 and Test matches.

COVID – 19 its impact on Cricket Economy:

The global economic slump caused by the Covid-19 pandemic could change the entire sports industry across the world. Some sports will be hit harder than others. The economic structure of international cricket is likely to change and lower-ranked nations would certainly face a crunch in funds. On the other hand other sports like hockey, golf, table tennis would have uncertain future in India. The key revenue generation for sports bodies is through licensing of television broadcast rights. With the stoppage in sporting events, it is likely that most sporting bodies will face financial hits. Indian cricket could be relatively better placed. Smaller countries like West Indies, Bangladesh and Sri Lanka could face challenges if their respective media contracts are not renewed. Therefore, corona 19 would have very big impact on the cricket world. Furthermore, Sports other than cricket might find it harder to return to normal in India, because they do not have as deep financial support.

The Cricket Australia to lose \$174 million due to the corona virus. Outbreaks derail the high-profile home Test series against India later this year. It now remains to be seen if India will play an extended series instead. There's also the potential cancellation of the World T20 tournament.

Right now the richest cricket boards are also facing huge losses due to outbreak of corona-19. So, cricket is not playing anywhere in the world.

Because of the cancellation of the IPL due to covid-19 the BCCI is losing around Rs 3,000 crores. It is really an irreparable loss to BCCI. Tens of thousands of people who are directly or indirectly connected to IPL have lost their jobs. Support staff and workers, logistic companies, airlines and hotels are some of the sectors that are adversely affected. As a result will have an effect on the Indian economy as well. The 2015 IPL contributed Rs 1,150 crores to the Indian GDP. However, due to Covid-19 the cricket world is losing thousands of corers.

Result of the Study:

The finding of article is that covid-19 has caused huge loss to global cricket in general and more particularly to BCCI. According to the reports due delayed of IPL matches the BCCI may incur more than Rs.3500 crores loss.

Conclusion:

Right now cricket is not playing anywhere in the world due to the outbreak of Covid-19. Cricket is a crowd puller game. Millions of peoples are watching live cricket matches all over the world. Now, for the past four months cricket has been paralyzed, because of Covid-19. In India cricket is the most popular game and it generate huge revenue to our economy. Ever since the launch of IPL in India has virtually changed the phase of cricket in India. The performance of players has been tremendously improved and the entire world is looking at our players. However the outbreak of the deadly virus had adversely affecting the global cricket economy.

References:

1. B. G. Clarkson, A. Culbin, S. Pope "Covid-19: Reflections on threat and uncertainty for the future of elite women football in England-Taylor & Francis-2020

2. R. Schinke, A. Papaioannou, K. Hensiksen, G. Si, Zhang "Sports psychology services to high Performance athletes during Covid-19 " Taylor & Francis – 2020
3. S. Feng, C. Shen, N. Xia, W. Song, M. Fan "Rational use of face masks in the Covid-19 pandemic" - The Lancet Respiratory – 2020
4. Vaishnavi Kanukurti, "The Economics of the Indian premier League" India folk.com 2019
5. W. J. McKinnon, R. Fernando" The Global Macro Economic Impacts of Covid-19" Seven Scenario - papers.ssrn.com – 2020
6. What is the Corona Virus lockdown impact on various sports - The New Indian Express - Indian express .com - 2020